

s-Triazolo (5,4-b)naphtho(2,1-d)thiazole A Novel Heterocyclic System

J. V. SINGH

Department of Explosives, Pub-Sarania, Gauhati-3

Manuscript received 12 July 1973; accepted 10 September 1973

A hitherto unreported system, s-triazolo(5,4-b)naphtho(2,1-d)thiazole, has been synthesised starting from β -naphthylamine. Tetrazolo(5,4-b)naphtho(2,1-d)thiazole¹, an already known system, has been synthesised by an alternate route.

2-HYDRAZINOBENZOTHIAZOLE has been reported to react with formic acid and nitrous acid to yield triazolo(2,1-b)benzothiazole and tetrazolo(2,1-b)benzothiazole respectively². An approach to the naphtho(2,1-d)thiazole series gave s-triazolo(5,4-b)naphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (I) and tetrazolo(5,4-b)naphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (II). II has already been prepared from diazotised 2-aminonaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole by reaction with sodium azide.

I

Refluxing a mixture of VII and formic acid for three hours gave the parent compound I in 60% yield. A solution of VII in dilute acetic acid on treatment with sodium nitrite gave II in somewhat low yield.

Experimental

Melting points (taken in heating bath) are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were measured on nujol mulls.

II

Bayer³ *et al.* have reported the formation of 2-hydrazinonaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (VII) by heating 2-hydroxy-, 2-halogeno- or 2-sulphonic acid derivatives of naphtho(2,1-d)thiazole with hydrazine hydrate. 2-Chloronaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (VI) was prepared by Hunter and Jones⁴ directly from β -naphthylisothiocyanate by heating with phosphorus pentachloride in a sealed tube. This method is impracticable because β -naphthylisothiocyanate is always obtained in low yields. In the present investigation, VI was obtained by the reaction of sulphuryl chloride on 2-mercaptanaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (V) in 70% yield. The already reported method of preparing V makes use of heating β -naphthylamine with carbon disulphide and sulphur in a bomb and the yields were fairly low⁵. We made use of an alternate method which involves the reaction of 2-amino-1-thionaphthol (IV) with carbon disulphide in alcohol and gives 80% yields. IV was obtained by the reduction of 2-amino-1-thiocyanatnaphthalene⁶ (III), with sodium sulphide⁷ and was used in the crude state.

The synthesis of parent compounds (I and II) has been achieved as follows: see (Fig. 1)

2-Mercaptanaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (V):

2-Amino-1-thiocyanatnaphthalene (III, 20.0 g., 0.1 mole) was added in small portions to a boiling solution of sodium sulphide (Na₂S, 11.7 g., 0.15 mole) in water (100 ml.) during 30 min. and the mixture was further heated under reflux for 1 hr. After cooling the mixture was neutralised with acetic acid and the semisolid mass thus separated was extracted with ether, washed thoroughly with water and dried (MgSO₄). Ether was removed by distillation and the residual thiol (IV, 15.0 g.) was heated under reflux with carbon disulphide (30 ml.) and alcohol (10 ml). A yellow crystalline mass started separating after 3 hr. After 18 hr., the mixture was cooled and the solid mass collected, washed with ether, dried and crystallised from alcohol, yield (15.2 g.) (70%), m.p. 245° (Lit.⁸-m.p. 240°).

2-Chloronaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (VI):

2-Mercaptanaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (V, 6.51 g., 0.03 mole) was added to sulphuryl chloride (20 ml.) and the mixture was kept at room temperature for 1 hr. The mixture was then just heated to 50°, cooled and

Fig - I

poured onto crushed ice. The solid was filtered, washed with water and dried. It was crystallised from alcohol, yield 5.3 g. (80%), m.p. 78° (Lit.⁴ m.p. 80°).

2-Hydrazinonaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (VII) :

2-Chloronaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (VI, 4.4 g., 0.02 mole) was added in small portions to hydrazine hydrate (80%, 30 ml.) at reflux during a period of 30 min. and the mixture was further heated for 3 hr. On cooling, a crystalline solid separated which was filtered, washed with water and dried. It was crystallised from aq. alcohol, yield 3.2 g. (75%), m.p. 220° (Lit.³ m.p. 222°-3°). I.R. 3320, 3200 cm^{-1} (NH S), 3040 cm^{-1} (CH arom.), 1660, 1625, 1575 cm^{-1} (C = C, C = N, N = N).

s-Triazolo(5,4-b)naphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (I) :

2-Hydrazinonaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (VII, 2.15 g., 0.01 mole) was heated under reflux with formic acid (30 ml.) for 3 hr. After cooling, the mixture was poured onto crushed ice. The solid mass was collected, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, yield 1.35 g. (60%), m.p. 235°. (Found : C, 63.82; H, 3.02; N, 18.18; S, 13.72. Calc. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{S}$, C, 64.00; H, 3.11; N, 18.66; S, 14.22%) I.R. 3100, 3060 cm^{-1} (CH arom.), 1600, 1510, 1500 cm^{-1} (C = C, C = N).

Tetrazolo(5,4-b)naphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (II) :

A solution of 2-Hydrazinonaphtho(2,1-d)thiazole (VII, 2.15 g., 0.01 mole) in acetic acid (50%, 30 ml.)

was cooled to 10°. A solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g., 0.01 mole) in water (10 ml.) was added to the above solution. The tetrazolo compound started separating at once. After keeping at room temperature for 1 hr., the dark brown product was filtered, washed thoroughly with water, dried and crystallised from aq. alcohol, yield 0.09 g. (40%), m.p. 113° (Lit.¹ m.p. 114°). IR 3100, 3060 cm^{-1} (CH arom.), 1620, 1590, 1520, 1470 cm^{-1} (C = C, C = N, CN = N).

1. V. YA. POCHINOK, S. D. ZAITSEVA and R. G. EL'GORO, *Ukrain. Khim. Zhur.*, 1951, 17, 509; *Chem. Abs.*, 1954, 48, 11393b.
2. G. A. REYNOLDS and J. A. VANALLAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 1478.
3. O. BAYER, H. HERDIECKERHOFF and H. SCHINDHELM, U.S. Pat., 2,073,600 (to I.G. Farbenind. A.G.); *Chem. Abs.*, 1937, 31, 3300^a.
4. H. G. HUNTER and J. WM. T. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 941.
5. K. TAKUZO and M. SHUNICH, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1942, 45, 957.
6. H. P. KAUFMANN and W. OEHNING, *Ber.*, 1926, 59b, 187; *Chem. Abs.*, 1926, 20, 1603.
7. A. RICCI and N. CAGNOLI, *Ann. Chim. (Rome)*, 1955, 45, 172; *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, 50, 5564c.
8. HEILBRON and BURBURY, *Dictionary of Organic Compounds*, Vol. 4, p. 2075. Eyer and Spottiswood, London, 1953.